

PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS OF FINDING FEELINGS OF TOLERANCE IN CHILDREN DURING GAME ACTIVITY

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Abstract: This article provides insights into the pedagogical mechanisms of developing children's feelings of tolerance during play, information about the role of play in preschool educational organizations and its strengthening.

Key words: game, intellectual, education, tolerance, society, complex, pedagogue, environment.

Insights into the pedagogical mechanisms of developing children's feelings of tolerance during play, information about the role of play in preschool educational organizations and its strengthening. It is important that not only the indicators, but also the human and his social and spiritual interests should stand.

If the final goal of development and the criterion of its effectiveness depend on such factors as expanding the opportunities of society members, meeting their material and spiritual needs, and achieving a high standard of living, then its beginning is combined with the prospects of educational reforms implemented in the country. goes Therefore, in the 21st century, it is recognized that economic growth is not the main goal. That is, society's income is only a means of providing people's vital needs. As the great Greek thinker Aristotle said, "It is clear that wealth is not the real goal we are after, it is simply the desire to have something useful and special." In fact, the stability of the country's development, the effectiveness of reforms in all spheres of society and, ultimately, ensuring a high level of economic development directly depend on the education system and its level. After all, education is considered a component of human development, the main factor in solving society's problems. In other words, education as a

component of human development has an unparalleled effect on the elimination of a number of social, economic, and political problems.

In our republic, the education system is always under the attention of the state. During the past period, complex organizational and legal measures were implemented to create an effective preschool education system aimed at ensuring the formation of a healthy and comprehensively developed generation.

Many social education goals can be realized by creating a child-friendly environment in the educational process. In particular, to attract all children to the educational institution, regardless of their social background; ensuring the full involvement of children of low-income, bereaved families and others in education; the physical and intellectual differences of children are taken into account, and an environment is created in preschool education; ensuring that all children have equal opportunities in the educational process, etc.

In fact, tolerance has been formed in the history of mankind as a criterion of tolerance and respectful attitude towards other religions and nations. Because tolerance means an unbiased attitude towards traditions, culture, views and ideologies, it recognizes the diversity of the world.

But in fact, tolerance as a very broad concept fully manifests itself in the system of historical, spiritual and educational values developed in Central Asia. During its rich and long history, our nation has experienced many events, which in itself left a significant mark on its material, spiritual culture, socio-economic and spiritual life.

Tolerance and nationalism should be considered as such a phenomenon that they did not appear by themselves in a few years by moving from one place to another or by introducing them, it is a product of history. It is necessary to look for the roots of these events in the distant history of our nation.

Entering preschool is a huge turning point for every child. From this period, the child in the family is obliged to perform not only family relations, but also

private tasks necessary for his personality. With this, his role in the family does not seem to decrease, but on the contrary, it increases. That is, the period of protecting his reputation not only among family members, but on the contrary, among society, with his personal actions begins. However, the child will not be able to understand this yet.

Even simple concepts leave a mark on everyone at different speeds and powers. This phenomenon is primarily related to a person's personality, abilities and age.

Tolerance as a social phenomenon is a social interaction between workers and the state and society. It is also reflected in their attitude towards their organizations. According to the nature of the content, such relations consist of proposals and recommendations created by the people's concern to attract the attention of the leaders of the state and public organizations to an important issue, to give importance to the problem based on the demands of justice or speed, without a pressure approach to the issue. This form of the phenomenon of tolerance is in the form of an objection or recognition of the content of the processes of managing the development of social events, and the attitude of the omrn in this regard is distinguished by its logicalness, conciseness, and indicative nature of the solution of the problem.

The view of tolerance as a form of manifestation of opinions is closely related to the task of mass control of society. The way of mass control of changes in social life, according to its essence, consists of several appearances and forms. They can be conditionally classified as follows: a) system of dialogues in the order of state offices and institutions, mutual relations and tolerance expressed in meetings; in particular, respect for colleagues and leaders - obedience, thoughtfulness; b) attitude to the opinions expressed about everyday life, usual events and events. To approach issues with patience, express one's opinion with concern; c) tolerance manifested in the family environment, in the circle of friends, in the circle of like-

minded people. In particular, the manifestation of the characteristics of not putting one's own interests first, not beating the character of others to the ground; g) exchanges of ideas on social issues that occur during weddings and events. For example: manifestation of the characteristics of kindness, honesty, faith, sympathy, equality, prudence, loyalty. According to Abu Rayhan Beruni's point of view, the emergence of tolerance is inextricably linked with social relations, people's way of life, material needs, interests, interests, demands and goals. For example, blindness among people arose due to the need of people to get rid of the needs of mutual association and external dangers together. Beruni also notes that tolerance has gained historical importance in ensuring the viability of peoples.

The famous philosopher of the East, Abu Nasr Farabi, writes about tolerance: "There are no natural or voluntary ties between some people, it is necessary for each person to harm the interests of the state for his own benefit, and one must be a stranger to another. , because even if they unite, they unite because of necessity and obligation, even if they reach a compromise, they think that they will only come to an agreement when one of them wins and the others lose. In this, they are forced to come to an agreement under the pressure of an external force. One of the animal beliefs characteristic of humanity is this belief"¹². It can be seen from Farabi's thoughts that he emphasizes the need for people to live together not by force, but by choice, so that mutual conflicts will stop, and they should live in cooperation. Or again: " Some people think that the bonds of connection between people are based on the common behavior, nature, verb and language of these people. Each nation has its own characteristics.

It is important to ensure that the same upbringing of children continues in educational organizations. It is expedient to pay special attention to this during training in activity centers organized in pre-school educational organizations. After all, it is important for children to grow up well, and for their future relationships to be creative.

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